

SAUDI CLERICS RESPONSE TO BAHRAIN PROTESTS IN 2011: EXPLORING DUALITY

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Abstract:

The popular protests that began in Tunisia in December 2010 ignited a domino effect across the Arab World. While in Tunisia and Egypt it led to political change, in Syria and Libya it escalated into civil war between the warring factions. However, the impact of Arab Spring remained limited in the oil rich Gulf States except Bahrain where protests turned into a violent clashes between regime forces supported by the Saudi military and the protesters.

The Arab Spring protests had set off a debate among the religious circles inside Saudi Arabia, where both establishment clerics and the independent one took a supportive stand to the protesters in Syria, while at the same time condemned the protesters in Bahrain. This study examines the factors that shaped contrasting responses of Saudi clerics and explores the reasons behind their dichotomous response to the unfolding events in Bahrain.

Keyword: arab spring, bahrain, saudi arabia, religious clerics

Introduction

The roots of the Bahraini protests lie in its history, economy and demography. Unlike other neighbouring Gulf States where Arab Spring protests were rather muted, in Bahrain they reached the level of open uprising that resulted in a violent crackdown. The ruling Al-Khalifa family of Bahrain belongs to the Sunni sect of Islam, while as per the unofficial estimates the Shiite population ranges around sixty per cent. Historically Shiites had problems with the regime on the issue of political reforms. During the 1980s and 1990s, the Bahrain witnessed repeated outbreaks of Shiite protests demanding reforms. What happened

during the Arab Spring protests was closely linked to this past activism in shaping the perspective of Saudi Arabia.

The protests were not unexpected in Bahrain as it had a history of protests since the 1980s which led to the introduction of the new constitution in 2002. While its demography played an important role in fuelling the protests, its proximity to the oil rich eastern province of Saudi Arabia further complicated the situation. It had a spillover effect on Shiite population of the eastern region of Saudi Arabia, that could pose a challenge to the Saudi hegemony in the Gulf. The events of Arab Spring had already ignited a discussion among religious circles of Saudi Arabia and several of non-establishment clerics with former *sahwa* background initially welcomed the changes showed their support to the aggrieved protesters. On the other hand, state aligned clerics of religious establishment had criticised the protesters and blamed them for fomenting discord in the community.

The uprising, though, started as popular protests and supported by a few Sunnis in the beginning transformed into full-blown sectarianism. The historical claim of Iran over Bahrain and the Shiite protesters became a problem later on. Saudi and Bahraini authorities systematically played the sectarian card from the beginning and blamed Iran for the unrest which to kept the Sunnis away from the protests. The government kept on airing the sectarian propaganda through official media while Saudi Arabia and other GCC states too continued to blame Iran for interfering in Bahrain. For Saudi Arabia, any political reform in Bahrain meant the empowerment of the Shiites, which could directly have an effect on kingdom's Shiite population of the eastern province. Saudi Arabia successfully used the sectarianism as an instrument of foreign policy to provide legitimacy to its actions, as blaming Iran and Shiites enabled it to receive the support from the religious clerics.

The Arab Spring in Bahrain

In February 2011, when wave of Arab Spring protests swept through Tunisia and Egypt, Arab Spring made its presence in Bahrain. The fall of Hosni Mubarak in Egypt on 11 February inspired thousands of Bahraini youth activists who declared 14 February to call people for the peaceful protests in Manama and called it the 'Day of Rage' (ICG, 2011). A day before the demonstration youths had widely circulated their demands on social media platforms. Initially, the focus of the protests was to rewrite

the constitution of 2002, which has failed to bring any significant reform and for the investigation on claims of corruption, naturalisation and the allegations of torture on activists who had been arrested in recent years (*Gulf News*, 2011). The king perturbed by the demands had announced a grant of US\$2,650 (1000 BD) to each family to celebrate the anniversary of the charter (Noueihed & Warren, 2012: p. 151).

On 14 February, the size of demonstration was not very large and the protestors refrained from criticising the king and only asked for the limited political demands (BICI, 2011:p.68). There was no call for a regime change or any sign of sectarianism, even though the majority of the demonstrators were Shiites but the brutal crackdown of the demonstrators surprised many and one person was killed on the first day and another was killed during his funeral procession (Kerr & Jones, 2011). This further inflamed the anger as protestors received the public sympathies.

The opposition which did not take part directly in the demonstration also came out in support. Members of the Al-Wefaq, the most significant opposition block, which until then had no role in the organisation of the protests, resigned from the parliament and most of the Shiite judges and ministers resigned in protest against the crackdown (*Al-Arabia*, 2011). Encouraged with Al-Wefaq's support, thousands of the demonstrators marched towards Pearl Square in the centre of Manama and government institutions came under daily blockades (BICI, 2011:p.71). The authorities responded harshly and on 17 February the forces cracked down the protestors assembled at Pearl Roundabout in the early hours and cleared the sites.

Since the initial days of the protests, the Bahraini authorities had meticulously pushed its narrative of the events to form public opinion, especially among the Sunni population of the country. The regime's apprehension about the Shiite majority was not new and goes back to the immediate aftermath of the Iranian Revolution. Though Iran did not provoke the 2011 protests, but Supreme Leader Ali al-Khamenei's call for moral support in his 2 March 2011 speech complicated the situation (Zarrabi-Khashani, 2014). The Iranian interference played into the hands of the Bahraini authorities which was projecting the opposition movement as sectarian. The state media aired a non-stop propaganda

campaign on the state-controlled Bahrain TV depicting the demonstrators as ‘traitors’ who are instigating violence against the state (D’Almeida, 2011).

Initially, the Sunnis also joined the Shiite protesters and mainly the moderate faction supported the demands of the protesters in the interest of all citizens (Abdo, 2013:p.14). However, this cooperation could not be sustained in the long term as Sunnis were won over by the regime’s narrative and increasingly disinclined to cooperate with the majority Shiite opposition groups (Ibid.). The delicate Shi’a-Sunni partnership was further strained when Shiite protesters marched towards the royal palace. Despite warning from the pre-dominantly Shiite al-Wefaq party, two days after this march, protestors cut off the road leading to the Manama international airport and tried to stop people from going towards the financial harbour of the capital. In addition, they also cut off the road to the King Fahd Causeway, a vital link connecting Bahrain with Saudi Arabia (*Al-Jazeera*, 2011).

This pitched the Shiites and Sunnis against one another and those Sunnis who were initially supporting the protesters were now compelled to think about their position. The continuous sectarian narrative unleashed by the regime and the subsequent escalation strengthened the regime’s claims of the demonstrations being a sectarian conflict. This forced Sunnis to choose between the state and the demonstrators (Abdo, 2013: p.14). The divide came out open in the daily lives of Bahrainis and pitched battles erupted when police tried to clear the highway. It convinced the Sunnis to rally behind the royal family. Ali Fakhro, a former education minister, narrated that people began boycotting the restaurants owned by Shiite and for first time people started identifying themselves as Shi'a and Sunni.ⁱ

The deteriorating relations between Shiites and Sunnis further consolidated the sectarian discourse on the ground. The protests began with the demand of economic and political reforms, transformed into a tug of war between two regional powers—Islamic Republic of Iran and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Though Iranian government did not have any role in the protests but Iranian media added fuel to the fire by openly backing the Shiite demands in these circumstances (Khalaji, 2011). With Saudi Arabia already backing the Sunni royal family (Abdo, 2013:p.15),

ⁱ Fakhro, Ali Interviewed by Geneive Abdo, Manama, March 2012 for Saban Centre for Middle East Policy Analysis Paper Number 29, April 2013.

the country became a proxy battleground for the two regional powers. Consequently, the perception that Bahraini opposition is a Shiite rebellion to seize power from the Sunnis was firmly established (Ibid.).

On 14 March Saudi troops and National Guard arrived in Bahrain through King Fahd Causeway, along with the UAE police personnel and some Qatari troops (ICG, 2011). The action was based on the GCC Joint Defence Agreement, signed in 2000 which declared that foreign aggression against any GCC member would be regarded as an attack on all GCC members and that other members have the obligation to offer military support from other members (Koch, 2010). The mandate of this force, known as 'Peninsula Shield Force' was to protect vital institutions, installations and government buildings which enabled the Bahraini security forces to concentrate on the demonstrators (BICI, 2011:p.134). However, the symbolic message was directed at the demonstrators and Iran that no change would be acceptable by other members of the GCC, especially Saudi Arabia.

Saudi-Bahrain Relations and Strategic Interests

The failure of the constitutional experiment in Bahrain in 1973 and with limited economic resources, Bahrain could not withstand a politically active population in the absence of the British. This compelled the ruling family to move closer to Saudi Arabia for help (Chubin &Tripp, 1992), financial constraints made it increasingly dependent on Saudi Arabia. Nearly 70 per cent of the Bahraini oil flowed from Saudi Arabia to Sitra oil refinery and both countries shared the profit from the Abu Saafa oil fields under an agreement concluded in 1972 (Woertz, 2018). With just sixteen miles off the east coast of Saudi Arabia, Bahrain had developed itself as a regional financial hub in the wake of Lebanese civil war (1975-1990). Though it is not an oil exporting country but it had increasingly benefited from the regional oil wealth, thanks to its one of the largest refinery in the world, BAPCO Sitra refinery. An oil pipeline connecting Saudi off shore oil field of Abu Saafa pumps most of the oil to its refinery. Riyadh's strategic and economic hold over Bahrain was further strengthened with the construction of the 25-kilometre-long King Fahd Causeway that connects al-Jasra in Bahrain and al-Aziziya in Saudi Arabia which was inaugurated on 26 November 1986.

Apart from oil Saudi Arabia has been a major trading partner of Bahrain, over the years Saudi Arabia had developed close trade relations with Bahrain. As per latest trade figures the trade exchange between both countries has reached \$3.9 billion in 2022 (*Arab News*: 2023: 15 May). Saudi Arabia has been a consistent investor in Bahraini industries like, construction, petrochemical, banking, Aluminium, and tourism. By 2011 when Arab Spring protests broke out, Saudi Arabia had made massive investments in various Bahraini projects. In fact, Saudis accounted for seventy per cent of annual tourists who travel to Bahrain and over thirty-four Saudi companies were based in Bahrain. And Saudi Arabia had invested nearly \$1.32 billion in Bahrain (Trade Arabia, 2011). A large number of Saudis use King Fahd Causeway to escape from the conservative environment of their kingdom and spend some leisure time in Bahrain. Saudi Arabia has always been wary of the developments in Bahrain and it has been described as the Saudi's 'Achilles heel' (Tomkyns, 1983), because of its fear of an elected parliament since 1973 experiment. It could explain why some Saudi tribesmen (three hundred in numbers) joined Bahraini Forces in 1974 (Tesh, 1975).

Impact of Iranian revolution and Shiite influence

The Islamic revolution of Iran in 1979 left a significant mark on the Shiite population of Bahrain and other Gulf states. The theory of *wilayat al-faqih* (vice regency of the jurist) propounded by Ayatollah Ruhollah Khomeini was institutionalised through a new constitution, adopted through a referendum held on 30-31 March 1979. This installed a political rule by religious clerics, which had lifted the morale of Shiite activists across the Gulf countries and attracted Shiites of the region towards a political movement. In the subsequent years Shiite protests frequently occurred against the ruling regimes of the region, notable among them was the alleged coup plot of Bahrain in 1981 (Nasr, 2006:p.93). This had raised alarm bells in neighbouring Saudi Arabia and other Sunni Gulf states as Khomeini had embarked on a mission to export the revolution (Noueihed & Warren, 2013: 141).

The demography of Bahrain also complicates the situation due to its large Shiite population. The official Bahraini census does not show the population data along the sectarian lines and indicate that 70.2 per cent of the population is Muslim (Bahraini Census, 2010). But 1941 census had included the sectarian data and reported Shiite as fifty-two per cent

while Sunni Muslims at forty-eight per cent (Qubain, 1955). Some sources like *The New York Times* reported Shiites to be around fifty-five per cent while Sunnis at forty-five per cent in 1981 (*The New York Times*, 1982). Accordingly, some who estimated the population based on available literature and data on Gulf observe that the Shiite population has been between sixty to seventy per cent (Matthiesen, 2013:p.3). However nearly all available sources estimate that Shiite population outnumber the Sunnis except in a 2011 report of *Al-Jazeera* which reported an official Bahraini documents which placed the Shiite population at forty-nine per cent and the Sunnis at fifty-one per cent (*Al-Jazeera*, 2011: 7 April).

The Iranian Revolution of 1979 had triggered protests in Bahrain in support of Khomeini (Al-Mdaires, 2002). The increased trend of Bahraini Shiites visiting Qom and raising issues of unemployment and social justice in the Friday sermons in mosques had added to the tension between Saudi Arabia and Iran (Bahri, 2000: p.131). The historical precedence of interference like, claim of Ayatollah Sadeq Rouhani of Iran about Bahrain historically being part of Iran and demand for an Islamic government in Bahrain similar to Iran (Youssif, 1987), and the foundation of Islamic Front for the Liberation of Bahrain (IFLB) in September 1979 further added to the fears of a potential interference from Iran.

For Saudi Arabia any Shiite surge in Bahrain was a potential threat to its oil rich eastern province that had a considerable concentration of the Shiite population. Since Wahhabi doctrine considered them as heretics, they had traditionally faced discrimination. A substantial number of Shiites worked as semi-skilled workers in the oil fields of the eastern province but the oil boom of the 1970s had not translated into socio-economic and educational improvement of the Shiite people. The discrimination was not only because they were considered as heretic but also being an aberration in the kingdom as a community (Al-Rasheed, 1998: p.131). During the 1979 revolution the Shiites of the kingdom took to the street to perform mourning rituals during the season of *ashura*, banned by the Saudi state since 1913. Saudi government had to use National Guards to disperse the mourners (Al-Rasheed, 2010: p. 142). Also, in 1981 Bahraini authorities accused Iran of supporting a coup plot by IFLB to install a theocratic state in Bahrain (Al-Hasan, 1993). It claimed that all conspirators were trained in Iran. Thus, this

historical legacy of Shi'a conspiracy to overthrow Sunni Gulf States has tagged the local Shiite population as a fifth column of Iran (Fuller & Francke, 1999: pp. 126-127).

The fall of Saddam Hussein in Iraq by US-led invasion in 2003 led to the rise of Shiite power in Iraq which made things more difficult for Saudi Arabia, losing Iraq was a big setback as it provided Iran an opportunity to spread its influence in Iraq which was later on called as 'Shi'a Crescent' (*NBC News*, 2008). Thus, any political transformation in Bahrain was a potential threat to the oil-rich eastern province of Saudi Arabia dominated by Shiites (Mabon, 2016). According to estimates, the Eastern Province comprises of thirty-three per cent of the Shia population (ICG, 2005). Therefore, Saudi Arabia could not afford the rise of Shiite influence in Bahrain; hence it had to act to prevent it. This is also reflected in the Saudi-Wahhabi religious literature which called Shiites as deviants and heretics.

Saudi Clerics Perspective

Within Saudi Arabia the religious clerics could not remain aloof from the events unfolding in Bahrain and other Arab capitals. While there was little impact of Arab Spring inside the kingdom but it had ignited a discussion about the events and the much-awaited reforms. Saudi Arabia itself had witnessed few reform petition movements in the 1990s and the early 2000s. While it did not bring any change in the status quo, but it did provide an opportunity to several non-establishment figures come out and voice their opinions, unlike the official religious institution's clerics who had always backed Al-Saud family.

Inside Saudi Arabia, apart from official state clerical establishment, there existed non-establishment religious clerics and groups; most notable among them was *sahwa* who came into prominence during the pro-reform movement of the 1990s. A movement emerged during the 1970s with the blend of Muslim Brotherhood ideology and Saudi-Wahhabi traditions (Lacroix, 2011: p.40). While government crackdown and imprisonment of its leader led to its disintegration. Some of its main leaders like Safar al-Hawali, Nasir al-Omar and Salman al-Awda were released by the government later on. These figures had left confrontationist attitude towards Al-Saud regime and returned to social activism and moral education (*tarbiya*). While most radical figures turned towards the extremism that resulted into violence against the Saudi regime during the

late 1990s (Lacroix, 2014), the other lesser-known figures had taken the path for a thorough reframing political system and creating a space for the constitutional democracy. This group was prominent during the post-Iraq war period in submitting another reform petition to the regime in 2003, calling for the constitutional reforms in the Kingdom (Elaph, 2003) But the wave of activism which resulted in the aftermath of the 11 September attacks came to an end by 2008. The mobilisation efforts by liberal Islamists had failed to bring any transformation in the Saudi political system. Their limited social base failed to attract the masses, unlike their senior *sahwa* predecessor who participated in the reform movement during the 1990s.

Other group of religious clerics that came into prominence in the aftermath of the 11 September attack were the traditional Wahhabi clerics who were not part of the state institutions but well respected among masses. Though politics was not their concern but deviation from the Wahhabi principles and the ideals of the Muhammad Ibn Abd al-Wahhab was unacceptable to them. These non-establishment clerics came into prominence with their criticism of ruling Al-Saud family and the official religious establishment for supporting the US war (Hegghammer, 2010). Which became source of inspiration to the violent extremists in the post 9/11 period.

The third group of clerics is part of Saudi religious establishment, which serves as the chief source of legitimacy for the Al-Saud family. These establishment clerics co-opted in the state apparatus under King Faysal had strengthened ties with the Al-Saud family after the 1979 Mecca insurrection by Juhayman al-Utaybi. They faced new challenges after the Gulf crisis of 1990-91. The opposition movement at that time forced them to align closely with the ruling authority to protect their own status and privilege. Under Ibn Baz, the religious establishment continued to act as the guardian of Wahhabi values and *shari'a*. The state supported religious institutions through increased funding but this also increased their dependence on state support for maintaining power and status in the society. While the state generally refrained from interfering in religious and social matters and often consulted the clerics, but mostly ignored their opinions.

In the aftermath of the 11 September attacks. The kingdom had come under strong global criticism, especially its state Wahhabi religious

discourse that was labelled as the root cause of the extremism. Under pressure the ruling authority had initiated the path of reform that was significantly encroaching upon the traditional domains of the state clerics. Moreover, in the absence of respectable figures like Ibn Baz and Saleh al-Uthaymin religious establishment now lacked any charismatic figure that command respect and large following among the masses. By the time protests hit the Arab capitals the establishment clerics had considerably lost their influence on social and educational spheres, as government was determined to push ahead on its reform path.

Saudi Establishment Clerics and the Protests

The state clerics of Saudi Arabia, who are part of its official religious establishment, were sceptical about the protesters since the beginning. The Committee of Senior Ulama, the highest religious body, issued a fatwa on 7 March 2011 against the demonstrations inside the kingdom and warned people against the wrath of God if they participated in the protests (*Al-Riyadh*, 2011). The position of official religious clerics was anchored in the traditional Wahhabi discourse which denounced any action against the ruler. In order to provide thrust to their opinion against the protesters the clerics revived and disseminated the opinions of Ibn Baz and Al-Uthaymin to call people to obey the rulers (*Al-Rasheed*, 2015:p.51). The religious establishment clerical also propelled the Iranian-Safavid-Shi'a conspiracy angle which as per them wanted to create discord in the kingdom and neighbouring Bahrain, reinforcing the age-old Wahhabi depiction of Shiites as heretics and agents of Iran. The state clerics warned people of bloodshed if they responded to the calls of the protests, and recalled the need of a consensus around the rulers (*Al-Rasheed: Ibid.*).

The committee's fatwa was circulated in the mosques and published extensively by the state media across the kingdom. The religious establishment was dismissive of the protests in various Arab capitals and dissuaded the Saudis not to play into the hands of the enemies of *umma* who want to destroy religion (*Al-Watan*, 2011: 5 Feb.). Grand Mufti travelled across the kingdom to deliver his sermon and warned the people. While Bahrain was facing protests, in the month of February 2011 Saudi grand mufti in his Friday sermon in Riyadh warned the youths and called the demonstrators as criminals who aimed to divide the people and destroy religious morals, and values. He also cited

prophetic hadith and said one who disobeyed the ruler he disobeyed the prophet (Al-Watan, 2011: 11 Feb.).

The establishment clerics worked in tandem with the state as it followed the same position adopted by the state. The regime used the fatwa of the committee to enforce ban on all type of demonstrations. The statement of Saudi Interior Ministry warning the protests (CNN, 2011) was reinforced by fatwa from the committee blaming protesters for creating sedition (*Saudi Gazette*, 2011). The establishment clerics followed the similar sectarian theme deployed by the regime, depicting the protests as sponsored by Iranian-Shiite forces (Wehrey, 2013: p.13) and branding all protesters as Shiites. It prevented any reconciliation between Shiite and Sunni as no Sunni activists would like to be linked with Shiites and Iran (Al-Rasheed, 2011). When Saudi forces militarily intervened in Bahrain to suppress the uprising and protect the Al-Khalifa rule, state clerics and religious corpus welcomed the regime's move.

However, in Syria where Saudi regime was backing anti-Assad rebels, the establishment clerics like Abd al-Muhsin al-Abad, Salih al-Fawzan including Grand Mufti declared the uprising as legitimate jihad but they cautioned Saudis not to travel to Syria to join the fight (Al-Aathar, 2012). Here too similar sectarian argument was brought against Shiite backed Alawite Asad's rule, projected as the oppressor of the Sunnis. Similarly in Yemen where Saudis launched a military campaign against Houthis, establishment clerics supported Al-Saud foreign policies. Mufti in his Friday sermon called for compulsory military service for the young men to prepare for jihad against the enemies of the nation and religion (*Al-Arabiya News*, 2015: 11 April). He also issued fatwa allowing Saudi soldiers to skip fasting in Ramadhan in order to wage 'jihad' against the enemy (International Business Times, 2015).

Non-Establishment Clerics Response

As mentioned earlier that apart from official establishment clerics, most notable non-establishment clerics and scholars that had emerged in Saudi Arabia belonged to *sahwa* group. Though group itself had declined after the government crackdown during the 1990s, and was disintegrated. However, prominent leaders released by the Saudi authorities had returned back to the social activism. Since the beginning of the Arab Spring protests, *sahwa* clerics assessment of the events was

different from the official Saudi religious establishment. They enthusiastically viewed the events and most of them backed the uprisings in Egypt and Tunisia (LMU, 2011). Salman al-Awda got his weekly TV show on MBC, *Al-Haya Kalima* (Life is a Word) cancelled by the authorities due to his of the uprisings in Egypt and Tunisia, he criticised Saudi government and media's handling of the Jeddah flood and called for more freedom (*Arabian Business*, 2011). The conservative figures like Nasir al-Omar expressed doubts and put forward a conspiratorial role of the West in these events (Al-Omar, 2011a).

Egypt and Tunisia

The fall of Ben-Ali in Tunisia and subsequent protests in Egypt were enthusiastically supported by these clerics. However, differences remained as Salman al-Awda explained in his book that revolution is a peaceful action which could only turned violent if those who are part of the revolution find it necessary to defend themselves. He elaborated on the role of the army in the peaceful revolution like Tunisia (Al-Awda, 2012:p.20). He considered that political oppression, economic deterioration, the decline in the standard of living are the reasons which cause a need in the people to change the system (Ibid: p.32). In his book, he praised the people's uprisings in Tunisia, Egypt, and Libya. He drew a comparison with the Abbasid revolution against the Umayyad, explaining it as a desire for change that had occurred in Islamic history (Ibid: p.42).

On the other hand, Nasir al-Omar was cautious in his response towards the Arab Spring in Tunisia and Egypt.ⁱⁱ While he praised the fall of Ben-Ali in Tunisia, he cautioned the revolutionaries in Egypt about the West. He supported the protesters but doubted the intentions of the West and Iran in post Mubarak Egypt. However, regarding change inside Saudi Arabia, both remained silent. They did not confront the ruling Al-Saud family or call for change in the political system. The other younger clerics comprised of liberal Islamists (as called by Lacroix) had also viewed the events as a historical opportunity to form a public stance in favour of a change in Saudi Arabia (Lacroix, 2014: p.9). These figures later on came together with other social and ideological groups in the

ⁱⁱ Nasir al-Omar, *التغيير في مصر.. وتجارة الإخوة الأعداء*, [Change in Egypt. and the trade of enemy brothers] 2011, <http://almoslim.net/node/141066>.

kingdom to draft reform petitions. Some of these clerics had also condemned the Saudi support for the military coup in Egypt, Al-Awda held that anyone who supports and finances the murderer is an accomplice and pointed at the Saudi regime by saying that it had been clear now who was driving Egypt to the destruction to save itself (Lynch, 2013).

Syria

On situation in Syria also these non-establishment clerics supported anti-Assad protesters but dominance of Alawites under Assad prompted them to view it on sectarian lines. Alawites, an offshoot of Shiite Islam, are also regarded as heretics by these clerics. The ideological foundations of these clerics were deeply-rooted in the Saudi-Wahhabi principles; therefore, it was obvious for them to express a uniform support to the Sunni Syrian opposition. However, there were diverse voices, while Nasir al-Omar argued for the religious war in Syria even when it was still at the initial stage, and stated the Syria event as religious war (*harb aqadiyya*) between Sunnis and Nusayris (term used for Alawites) (Al-Omar, 2011b). He also criticised the Alawite regime of al-Assad for oppressing the majority Sunnis and called Shiites and Jews as the allies of the Syrian regime (Al-Omar, Ibid.). Al-Awda on the other hand though backed the protesters but argued that matter should be left to the Syrians themselves (Al-Sharq Al-Awsat, 2012). He also dissuaded youths to travel to Syria as it would help Assad regime's narrative (Ibid.). Some *sahwa* clerics like Muhammad al-Arifi, Abd al-Aziz al-Turayfi began collecting funds for Syria which forced the authorities to prohibit them (Wehrey, 2012), while Abdullah al-Ghunayman even favoured Saudis to travel to Syria to fight against Assad (Al-Masriyyun, 2013).

Bahrain

This position dramatically changed once protesters took to the streets in Bahrain. This occurred not in far-away region like Syria, but it happened in the immediate neighbourhood of Saudi Arabia. While situation in Bahrain was similar to Syria but parties involved were just opposite vis-a-vis Syria, here Sunni Al-Khalifa ruler was facing protests from the majority Shiites. Since the beginning the Saudi and Bahraini governments were blaming Iran for the unrest and accusing it of interfering in Bahrain (Reuters, 2011; Washington Post, 2011). For *sahwa*, this was a

problematic situation as protesters in Bahrain were Shiites, unlike Syria, where majority Sunnis were the demonstrators. The theological differences between Wahhabism and Shi'a Islam are well known, the traditional Wahhabi discourse on Shiite beliefs consider them heretic and infidel. Al-Saud family too endorsed the same belief of Ibn Abd al-Wahab, which considers Shiites as a heretic (Bengio & Litvak, 2011). The *sahwa* clerics were too had evolved over the founding principles of Wahhabism, even though it had a Brotherhood world view, on the matter of religious beliefs they were the strict adherents of the Wahhabi creed.

Once uprising broke out in Bahrain the same rationale came out in the open; despite supporting the uprisings in other Arab states, like Egypt, Tunisia and Syria where the protesters and the opposition was Sunni, outside the kingdom, *sahwa* clerics adopted an opposite view on the uprising in Bahrain as the demonstrators were largely Shiites. The non-establishment clerics very much supported the official Saudi policy of military intervention and actively denounced the events happening at Pearl Square since the beginning of the protests (Lacroix, 2014:p.4).

Al-Omar in his statements issued observed that the situation in Bahrain was different from the events of Tunisia and Egypt and ascribed the events of those countries as a peaceful revolution by masses for freedom and dignity but called the events of Bahrain a sectarian chaos (*fitna taifiyya*) (Al-Omar, 2011). The statement of LMU accused the Shiite protesters of conspiring to eliminate Sunnis from Bahraini government and society; it not only called to the Sunni tribes of Bahrain not to leave Bahrain but urged them to unite.ⁱⁱⁱ Not surprisingly other clerics also supported the narrative of Saudi and Bahraini governments that demonstrations were instigated by Iran (Tareeq al-Islam, 2011). Given the influence they had with their association with the Saudi-Wahhabi traditions since the formative years, the socio-religious norms and theological discourse of *sahwa* clerics had always been rooted in Wahhabism which perceived Shiites as heretics (Al-Rasheed, 2011b). This was the reason when events unfolded in Bahrain, prominent *sahwa* clerics also like the establishment clerics blamed Iran and Hezbollah for spreading sectarianism in Bahrain (Tareeq al-Islam, 2011:Ibid.).

ⁱⁱⁱ "The League of Muslim Ulema warns of the Safavid tide emerging from Bahrain,"
رابطة علماء المسلمين تحذر سنة البحرين من هجرتها، والمد الصفوي (2011)
<https://almoslim.net/node/143526>.

Consequently, most *sahwa* clerics rejoiced at the intervention in Bahrain by the Saudi led GCC forces (Lacroix, 2014:p.4. Ibid).

Another prominent figure Salman al-Awda adopted a little different line. While calling the Bahraini demonstrators to stop the insurrection, he also championed for the legitimate rights of the minorities and called for coexistence (Al-Awda, 2011). He parted from the line of the official religious clerics in Saudi Arabia (Ibid.), who denounced the popular protests in their *fatwas* and called it a leap into chaos. Al-Awda came out with an exposition of a peaceful action while analysing the uprising under a Wahhabi background. In his book *Asilat al-Thawra* (Questions of the Revolutions) published in 2011 he tried to integrate the concept of revolution in the Saudi discourse.

Despite this, he could not prevent himself from viewing the Shi'a question through a political prism. He was dedicated to the unity of the *umma* and did not want to widen the division on theological and creedal differences with Shiites. In his book, he admired the uprisings in Tunisia, Libya and Egypt, but he kept a steady silence on the events happening in Bahrain, which was a Shi'a dominated country. In his media interaction, he continued to forewarn about the Shi'a political project (Al-Rasheed, 2015: p.86). According to Al-Awda, the differences in the Shi'a-Sunni beliefs differentiate them from each other and hence, like other Wahhabi clerics, he too considered Shiites as the rejectionists (*rafidha*) (Sagiyyeh, 2009). Not only he remained silent on Bahrain but he advocated the official Saudi narrative of the events that had labelled the uprising as an Iranian Shiite conspiracy to spread its influence in the Gulf and the eastern province of Saudi Arabia. Not only Al-Awda, a large number *sahwa* clerics condemned the Shiite protests inside Saudi Arabia (Matthiesen, 2012).

The clerics condemned the protests in Bahrain which was opposite to the position they had taken on uprisings in Syria (LMU, 2011b)^{iv}, Egypt (Islamic Umma Party, 2011) and Tunisia (Ibid.). The case of Syria was just opposite of Bahrain, where minority Alawite President ruled majority Sunni population, many among *sahwa* figures perceived the situation in Syria on sectarian line and regarded the rebels as defenders of Sunnis

^{iv} بيان من رابطة علماء المسلمين عن الأوضاع في سوريا *bayan min rabitat ulama al-muslimin an al-awdae fi suria*. [Statement by the Association of Muslim Scholars on the situation in Syria], <https://www.saaaid.net/fatwa/f82.htm>

against Alawite (Al-Rasheed, 2013). Staunch support to the rebels in Syria demonstrates the kind of extreme backing clerics showed to the Sunnis rebels of Syria. The most vocal among was Muhammad al-Arifi who even formed a committee to collect funds for the Syrian opposition groups and even favoured Saudis to travel to Syria to fight (Al-Masriyyun, 2013). When an Islamic Front was formed in Syria against the regime, most of the *sahwa* figures hailed it enthusiastically (Lacroix, 2014).

This dichotomy can be understood by examining the roots of the *sahwa* ideology and its view about the Shiites. The *sahwa* movement was the outcome of the blending of two diverse ideologies; the political discourse of the Brotherhood, which was brought by the Egyptian exiles into the kingdom, and the local Wahhabi tradition and norms. While *sahwa* leaders had a different world view than their traditional Wahhabi clerics, their daily lives and norms were hugely guided by the local Wahhabi traditions (Lacroix, 2011). Consequently, the same religious outlook also reflected in their perception about those who were not a follower of the Wahhabi doctrine. In this case, the Wahhabi perception of Shi'ism played a significant role in *sahwa*'s understanding of Shiite people.

The statements of some *sahwa* clerics provide an idea about their perceptions on Shiites; Muhammad al-Arifi, who in one of his speeches prayed to God to 'destroy pro-Shi'a Assad fighters' and several times in his comments on Twitter, he called Shiites as *rafidhi* (rejectionist) a derogatory term used by Wahhabis (HRW, 2017).^v Apart from him cleric Al-Omar had written a treatises on Shi'a Islam in 1993, declaring them as unbelievers and the enemies of Islam (Ibid.), also accused them of treachery (Al-Omar, 2012).^{vi} He viewed the Syrian conflict as a legitimate religious war where Assad regime was supported by Shiite and Jews (Al-Omar, 2011). Therefore, it was not unexpected that he viewed the Shiite demonstrators of Bahrain as a Shiite-Iranian plot to eliminate the Sunnis.

The harsh and critical discourse against the Shiites was common to all figures and varies on the degree of extremism of the perception of the

^v Mohammad al-Arifi (@MohamadAlarefe on the Twitter, 2 August 2012, Deleted now. <https://twitter.com/mohamadAlarefe/status/230954079768166401>.

^{vi} Nasser al-Omar (@naseralomar) on Twitter, 1 January 2012. <https://twitter.com/naseralomar/status/153473626669187072>.

individual. The religious discourse and norms of *sahwa* were imbibed from the local Wahhabi tradition which remained core to its beliefs. Consequently, when uprising erupted in Syria most of these clerics considered the rebels as a defender of Sunni resuscitation (Al-Rasheed, 2015: p.21). On the contrary, the same enthusiasm turned into trepidation when demonstrators took to Pearl Square in Bahrain. They viewed the Bahraini uprising as conspiracy of Shiite Iran to eliminate the Sunnis from the Gulf. Salman al-Awda was the only one who was somewhat different from the rest of other scholars and denied calling them non-Muslims and warned against clash (Fitzgerald, 2009). But he also could not completely detach himself from the well-grounded Wahhabi tradition and its perceptions of Shiites. He mostly remained silent about the events in Bahrain in his book *Questions on Revolution*. Even though he supported peaceful coexistence, he did not explicitly come out in support of the Bahraini protesters' demands and only called them to stop the demonstrations.

Conclusion

Bahrain was the only GCC country that experienced a large-scale protests during the Arab Spring unlike its other Gulf neighbours. The sectarian demography of Bahrain played an important role in fuelling the unrest while its proximity to Saudi Arabia further complicated the situation for the kingdom. While impact of Arab Spring was rather muted inside Saudi Arabia barring protests in the eastern province which is closed to Bahrain. The unfolding events in Tunisia and Egypt generated a discussion among the religious circles inside the kingdom. The response has been varied from Saudi religious establishment to the non-establishment clerics.

The Saudi establishment clerics including grand mufti followed the official Saudi position and criticised the protesters of Tunis, Cairo and Bahrain. While adhering to the sectarian argument by blaming Iran and Shiites for the unrest, they warned Saudis of chaos in case of disobedience to the ruler. The clerical corpus. Following the official Saudi policies in supporting the uprising in Syria against Bashar al-Asad, the establishment clerics declared it a 'legitimate' jihad against the oppressive regime. While on the situation in Bahrain they consistently propagated state narrative based on Shiite-Iran conspiracy, reinforcing

the religious rulings and age-old Saudi Wahhabi religious perception of the Shiites.

The independent non-establishment clerics had varied responses to the protests. Prominent *sahwa* Islamists like Al-Awda supported the protesters in Cairo, Tripoli, Damascus and Tunis, while conservatives like Nasir al-Omar remained suspicious despite of support for the protesters. However, these clerics also shared the traditional Wahhabi perspective on Shiites, consequently viewed the situation on sectarian terms.

The dichotomy these clerics became evident during the Bahraini uprising, which posed an ideological challenge due to Bahrain's demographics. While supporting uprisings in Syria, they denounced Shiite protesters in Bahrain and aligned with the official Saudi position on Bahraini. Despite of advocating coexistence, Al-Awda remained silent on Bahrain while others rejoiced when Saudis intervened. The traditional Wahhabi perception of Shiites profoundly influenced their perception of events in Bahrain, viewing Iran as a destabilising force and aligning with Saudi and Bahraini regimes to propagate the Iranian conspiracy angle.

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